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This is an **author produced version** of a paper published in:

Botanical Review 86.1 (2020): 76-92

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12229-020-09217-z>

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1 **Sporangia and Spores in the Fern Genera *Spicantopsis* and *Struthiopteris* (Blechnaceae,**
2 **Polypodiopsida)**

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41 **I. Abstract**

42 *Struthiopteris* (Blechnaceae) has recently been classified on the basis of molecular and
43 morphological evidence, and some of its species are now classified in the sister genus
44 *Spicantopsis*. However, the lack of studies on several important morphological features
45 impedes a sound assessment of their congruence with this new systematic arrangement, as well
46 as of their range of variation and taxonomic value in this group of ferns. Here we present a
47 study on the spores and sporangia using both light and scanning electron microscopy in
48 *Struthiopteris* and *Spicantopsis*, using samples of all their species, and almost all their varieties.
49 We provide full morphological descriptions of the spores and sporangia of all these taxa. We
50 point out the perispore structure and ornamentation and the number and the thickness of
51 stomium cells in the sporangium clearly distinguish both genera.

52 **II. Keywords:** annulus, *Blechnum*, capsule, ferns, perispore, rosette, SEM,
53 taxonomy.

54

55

56 III. Text

57 A. Introduction

58 The Blechnaceae is a lineage within the leptosporangiate ferns (Polypodiidae), which
59 comprises 25 genera and *ca.* 250 species, according to the most recent classifications (PPG I
60 2016; Gasper et al. 2016, Molino et al. 2019b). Most of these genera were previously
61 included in *Blechnum* (Kramer et al. 1990). One is *Struthiopteris* Scop., which consists
62 mainly of small- to medium-sized plants, with pinnate, dimorphic fronds. Based on both
63 morphological and molecular information, some species of *Struthiopteris* have been recently
64 classified in *Spicantopsis* Nakai (Nakai 1933; Molino et al. 2019b).

65 *Spicantopsis* and *Struthiopteris* both contain few species and are restricted to the Northern
66 Hemisphere. *Spicantopsis* has three species, all of them restricted to Asia (Chiou et al. 1994;
67 Faguo et al. 2013): two are endemic to Japan, *Spicantopsis amabilis* (Makino) Nakai, and *S.*
68 *niponica* (Kunze) Nakai (with a variety named *S. niponica* var. *minima* Tawaga), and a third
69 one, *S. hancockii* (Hance) Masam., occurs in both Japan and Taiwan. *Struthiopteris*, in its
70 current circumscription, comprises 3 species. The first one is *Struthiopteris spicant* (L.)
71 Weiss. is widely distributed in two disjunct centers: one of them in Europe, where it is very
72 common in the west and center of the continent, and less frequent in the eastern part, the
73 Macaronesian archipelagos, and also in North Africa, and a second center in the Pacific coast
74 area of the United States and Canada. This species is a quite variable entity for which several
75 subspecies and varieties have been proposed; currently, two of them are accepted, *S. spicant*
76 var. *homophyllum* (Merino) Gabriel y Galán & R. Pino and *S. spicant* var. *pradae* S. Molino
77 & Gabriel y Galán (Molino et al. 2019a). The second species is *S. fallax* (Lange) S. Molino,
78 Gabriel y Galán & Wasowicz, which is endemic to Iceland (Molino et al. 2019a); and the
79 third species is *S. castanea* (Makino & Nemoto) Nakai, endemic to Japan (Fig. 1).

80 Reproductive structures in the sporophyte have long been known to render good characters in
81 fern taxonomy. However, different authors have used different terminology to refer to the
82 structures of the sporangia (Atkinson 1893; Bower 1928; Haider 1954; Wilson 1959;
83 Lellinger 2002; Prada et al. 2016). To clarify this terminology, here we will use what is stated
84 in Wilson (1959) and Lellinger (2002) with modifications from Prada et al. (2016), focusing
85 on the following sporangial traits: number of cells of the pedicel and the presence of a rosette
86 between the pedicel and the capsule, which is formed by the apical cells of the pedicels that
87 are different in their sizes and wall composition, *sensu* Prada et al. (2016); the structure of the
88 annulus *sensu* Wilson (1959), which is the sum of the mechanic cells (arcus), the structure of
89 the stomial area (formed by the epistomium, the hypostomium and the lips *sensu* Prada et al.
90 (2016) and the presence of posterior basal cells (between the arcus and the pedicel in the
91 posterior part of the capsule, opposite to the stomium area, term introduced by us) (Fig. 2).
92 Spores have been used also to separate fern taxonomic groups, thus becoming an extremely
93 important source of character traits with taxonomic relevance, mainly the spore dimensions,
94 the model of laesura, and the perispore ornamentation and structure (Olsen and Gullvag 1974;
95 Lugardon 1974; Barrington et al. 1986; Tryon and Lugardon 1991; Palacios-Rios et al. 2017).
96 Despite the low number of species of both *Spicantopsis* and *Struthiopteris*, and the fact that
97 their morphology, distribution and cytotaxonomy is comparatively well known (e.g. Nakai,
98 1933; Löve & Löve 1968; Nakato, 1987; Horjales et al. 1990), data on sporangia and spore
99 traits are scarce and incomplete. A recent publication (Prada et al. 2016) dealt with the
100 sporangia of 47 species of *Blechnum* L. s.l., and examined characteristics of pedicels,
101 rosettes, annuli, arcus and stomial areas. However, this comprehensive work only considered
102 one of the species of our interest, *S. spicant*, characterizing in the sporangia the length of the
103 pedicel, the number of cells of the arcus, and the number of cells of the stomial area.

104 Information about these characters are unknown in the other taxa of *Struthiopteris* and
105 *Spicantopsis*.

106 The spores of both genera have received a little more attention in the past. By far, *S. spicant*
107 is again the most investigated of all the taxa considered here, and its spores have been
108 described in several papers, including details of their size, ornamentation, and structure
109 (Lugardon 1965; Tryon and Lugardon 1991; Passarelli et al. 2010). However, this
110 information deals only with the typical variety of this extremely diverse entity, and no other
111 data are available for the rest of taxa. The spores of most of the Japanese species
112 (*Struthiopteris castanea*, *Spicantopsis niponica* and *S. amabilis*) have been only very briefly
113 described by Mitui (1979), who provided some SEM photographs. Moran et al. (2018), in its
114 phylogenetic and evolutionary study, included also some information about the spores of
115 other taxa within the family Blechnaceae. As far as we know, *Struthiopteris fallax* and
116 *Spicantopsis hancockii* lack any published data on their sporangia or spores.

117 The goal of this study is to provide new, comprehensive descriptions of the sporangia and the
118 spores of *Spicantopsis* and *Struthiopteris*, and assess their value for distinguishing the two
119 genera.

120

121 **B. Materials and methods**

122 We used both plants from new field collections and preserved material of several herbaria. In
123 the former case, a voucher specimen has been deposited in the herbarium MACB. We
124 obtained samples of all the taxa of interest except *Spicantopsis niponica* var. *minima*, since
125 the only material we had access to was an isotype, and we decided not to damage the
126 specimen while extracting sporangia and spores. Appendix 1 shows basic voucher
127 information regarding plant material.

128 Sporangia observations were obtained from at least five sporangia of at least two different
129 individuals per taxon, depending on the available material, following standard procedures for
130 sample extraction, staining and microscope preparation, widely used for these purposes
131 (Ruzin 1999; Passarelli et al. 2010; Palacios-Rios et al. 2017). All the observations were
132 made under an optical microscope (OM) *Nikon Labophot-2*. Exospore dimensions have been
133 measured in 20-30 spores under the OM from at least two individuals per taxa. We measured
134 and described the following traits: major and minor equatorial diameters of spores, perispore
135 ornamentation, and perispore structure.

136 Fine details about the sporangia and about the ornamentation and structure of perispore and
137 exospore of spores were obtained with scanning electron microscope (SEM) techniques.

138 Sample preparation followed standard protocols (Nation 1986), making two samples from
139 two different individuals per taxon. The observations were made with a SEM *Hitachi S-*
140 *3000N* operated at 20 kv, with a ESED (environmental secondary electron detector) coupled
141 to an X-ray dispersive energy analyzer (INCAx-sight, *Oxford Instruments*). The SEM study
142 was done in the facilities at Universidad Autónoma de Madrid (Servicio Interdepartamental
143 de Investigación).

144 We adjusted the taxonomic terms of the structures observed to the standardized terminology
145 in Wilson (1959) and Lellinger (2002) with modifications from Prada et al. (2016), as has
146 been introduced before.

147 We described the sporangium by observing and checking traits from the pedicel (number of
148 cell-rows in the pedicel, characteristics of the rosette), the capsule (length of the capsule), and
149 the annulus (number of cells in the arcus, lips, epistomium, hypostomium and posterior basal
150 area of the annulus) (Fig. 2).

151 C. Results

152 a. Sporangia

153 The sporangia in *Spicantopsis* and *Struthiopteris* are of the Polypodialean type, a capsule
154 with a vertical annulus, sustained by a pedicel (Fig. 3). In all the species studied, the
155 sporangia present short pedicels, with a length of 2–3 rows of cells, which do not differ
156 notably between taxa. All of the taxa present a rosette in the pedicel (Fig. 3A–D). The rosette
157 differs from the rest of the pedicel cells in size and shape. This rosette shows no important
158 differences in size between taxa. The pedicel in cross section is composed by three cells in all
159 the species observed in this work (Fig. 4A).

160 The capsules are more or less spheroidal (Fig. 3A–D, Fig 4B–D), the length for each species
161 can be observed in Table 1. The annulus is vertical and incomplete, being interrupted at the
162 pedicel.

163 In all the taxa, a complex stomial area has been observed in the anterior part of the capsule,
164 between the pedicel and the end of the arcus. Within this area, the 2–5 central cells constitute
165 the lip, with thickened walls, along which the sporangium will open. The lip is composed of
166 4–5 cells in the case of *Spicantopsis* (Fig. 3A, C) and (2)3 cells in the case of *Struthiopteris*
167 (Fig. 3D; Fig. 4B–D). The cells of the lip are narrower in *Spicantopsis*, 5–10 (12.5) μm , than
168 in *Struthiopteris*, 12.5–17.5(37.5) μm . More infrequently, there are only 2 cells in the lip. All
169 the taxa studied present epistomium and hypostomium (Fig. 3A, C, D; Fig. 4B–D).

170 Another observed differential trait refers to the number of posterior basal cells of the annulus,
171 those situated between the posterior end of the arcus and the pedicel, opposite to the
172 hypostomium. In *Spicantopsis niponica* this area is formed by 3–4 cells (Fig. 3A, C) whereas
173 in the rest of the species of *Spicantopsis* and all the taxa within *Struthiopteris* the arcus
174 emerges in direct contact with the pedicel, i.e. no area of posterior basal cells differentiates
175 (Fig. 3B, D).

176 The arcus is manifest, with a number of cells ranging between 19–29 in *Spicantopsis* (Fig. 5
177 A–C) and 12–21 in *Struthiopteris* (Fig. 5D–H). Table 1 shows the values measured for each
178 taxa.

179

180 *b. Spore size and ornamentation*

181 The spores of all the taxa in *Spicantopsis* and *Struthiopteris* are monolete, plane-convex in
182 equatorial view, and elliptic in polar view (Fig. 6).

183 Spores of *Spicantopsis amabilis* present a dark brown perispore, not folded, with a verrucate-
184 granulate ornamentation; the laesura is slightly prominent, almost as long as the spore (Fig.

185 6A). *Spicantopsis hancockii* has spores with a pale brown perispore, not angular, covered by

186 numerous irregular tabications with granulate surface, anastomosed into an irregularly

187 reticulate ornamentation; in some parts of the spore the walls are covered by a thin, smooth or

188 granulate, external layer; the laesura is subterminal and not prominent (Fig. 6B).

189 The spores of *Spicantopsis niponica* present the same appearance as in *S. hancockii* but they

190 are larger and with the laesura slightly more prominent (Fig. 6C).

191 The spores of *Struthiopteris castanea* have a dark brown perispore, rugate, irregularly and

192 obtusely angular, not reticulate; laesura slightly prominent, thick, almost as long as the spore

193 (Fig. 6D), with the perispore sticking out above it. The spores of *Struthiopteris fallax* and *S.*

194 *spicant* are quite similar, with a pale brown perispore; which appears rugate, slightly angular,

195 with irregular wrinkles not anastomosing into areolae; in *S. fallax* the perispore is more

196 sharply angular and the laesura is almost as long as the spore (Fig. 6E, F). The spores of *S.*

197 *spicant* are slightly smaller than those of *S. fallax*. The spores of the varieties of *S. spicant*,

198 var. *homophyllum* and var. *pradae*, show the same characteristics of the typical variety (Fig.

199 6G, H).

200 Table 1 summarizes the main information about spore size and ornamentation for all taxa.

201

202 *c. Spore structure*

203 The spores of *Spicantopsis amabilis* (Fig. 7A, B) present a compact perispore, up to 5 μm
204 thick, with a complex internal structure, composed of microlamellae with a smooth surface,
205 anastomosed, forming an intermediate lacunar layer, covered by a thin external layer giving
206 the exospore a smooth ornamentation. *Spicantopsis hancockii* and *S. niponica* show also a
207 compact perispore, up to 5 μm thick, and with an exospore showing small, sparse bullae (Fig.
208 7C, D).

209 The three species of *Struthiopteris* (*S. castanea*, *S. spicant* including all its varieties, and *S.*
210 *fallax*) have spores with perispore up to 10–12 μm thick; the structure is alveolate, with an
211 inner layer of spongy appearance, an intermediate layer with alveoli, and an external smooth
212 layer covering the alveoli; the exospore shows no external ornamentation (Fig. 7E–H).

213 Table 1 shows the basic information regarding spore structure for all taxa.

214 In addition, it has been observed that in all the taxa studied the perispore comes off easily, so
215 is frequent to observe spores lacking half of the perispore (Fig 7).

216 **D. Discussion**

217 In this work we contribute with new and updated detailed morphological observations about
218 the sporophytic reproductive structures of *Spicantopsis* and *Struthiopteris*. We have been able
219 to study almost all of the infrageneric taxa currently accepted for both genera. Due to the very
220 recent resurrection of the genus *Spicantopsis* (Molino et al. 2019b), this information is
221 particularly relevant from a taxonomical perspective at the generic level. Part of the
222 information is new for all or some of the taxa within each genus, which thus aid in the fine
223 and comprehensive descriptions of these taxonomic entities.

224 Our observations of the structure of the sporangia agree with some general ideas for the
225 leptosporangiate ferns. For example, it has been traditionally reported that the normal number
226 row cells in the pedicel is 1-4 (Wilson, 1959). However, in a previous work about
227 Blechnaceae, Prada et al. (2016) observed that it varies from 2 (i.e. *Blechnum australe* L.) to
228 6 (i.e. *Telmatoblechnum serrulatum* (Rich.) Perrie, D.J.Ohlsen & Brownsey), but normally
229 with a number of 3 rows.

230 The data obtained here fall within this range established for the family.

231

232 Very few previous observations have been made regarding the number of cells in the arcus
233 for Blechnaceae, although it seems to be an important taxonomical character. It is the case,
234 for example, detected in this work, since this character allow us to distinguish between the
235 two genera treated, being the largest average number for *Spicantopsis*. Also, at a more
236 specific level, in the case of *Struthiopteris spicant* var. *spicant*, the data obtained here (12–18
237 cells) loosely agrees with previous reports (Prada et al. 2016), in which a number of 15–19
238 cells is given, with a normal value of 16.. The case of *Spicantopsis* is different: Nakai (1933),
239 in the original description of the genus, gave a number of 30–36 cells in the arcus, but in the
240 current study none of the specimens of any species have shown sporangia with more than 29
241 cells.

242 We also noticed the presence of posterior basal cells in *Spicantopsis niponica*, which differs
243 from the rest of the species within *Spicantopsis* and *Struthiopteris*. This character has been
244 used in fern taxonomy to discriminate species, for example in the case of European
245 *Polypodium cambricum* L., *Polypodium interjectum* Shivas and *Polypodium vulgare* L.
246 (Ormonde, 1986), so it could be an interesting specific character for *S. niponica*.

247 The size of the capsule is an interesting character too. In general, the capsules of the species
248 within *Spicantopsis* are larger than the ones within *Struthiopteris*, except in the case of *S.*

249 *castanea*, which has the biggest capsules of all of the taxa studied here. However, this is
250 probably due to its ploidy level, since it is a decaploid species, with the highest chromosome
251 number reported in Blechnaceae (Nakato, 1987), whereas the rest of taxa are diploid (Löve &
252 Löve, 1968; Nakato, 1987; Horjales et al 1990).

253 The best sporangial characters to separate the two genera seem to be the number and size of
254 the cells in the lips (Table 1). These cells are more numerous and narrower (<12.5 µm) in
255 *Spicantopsis*, and fewer and thicker (>12.5 µm) in *Struthiopteris*. The number of cells in the
256 lips has been already reported for *S. spicant* in Prada et al. (2016) and agrees with what has
257 been observed here.

258 Spores have been widely used to separate species and genera of the leptosporangiate ferns
259 (Tryon & Tryon 1982; Tryon & Lugardon 1991). In particular, the size, ornamentation and
260 wall structure of the spores are of high taxonomic value: size, ornamentation, walls structure:
261 within a reasonable biometric range, these characters are constant for each species, although
262 there is a considerable variation between species and upper taxonomic levels (Lugardon
263 1974; Tryon and Lugardon 1991).

264 In *Spicantopsis*, Mitui (1979) provided brief descriptions of some of the species (*S. niponica*
265 and *S. amabilis*), which are expanded here with concise details of ornamentation and
266 structure of perispore and exospore. The size of the spores reported by Mitui in his work is
267 slightly smaller than reported here. This may be due to the different ways in which the
268 samples have been measured: Mitui used cross sections after a fixation treatment, whereas in
269 this work we measured the spores directly through the optical microscope, without any
270 previous treatment.

271 Furthermore, the only information available about these traits in *S. hancockii* so far is the size
272 of the spores mentioned in some floras (Chiou et al. 1994; Faguo et al. 2013), which agrees
273 with the measurements reported here.

274 Our results indicate that *S. amabilis* has noticeable differences in its spores compared to those
275 of *S. niponica* and *S. hancockii*. This could contribute to morphologically support the
276 phylogenetic differences found between *S. amabilis* and a clade formed by the rest of species
277 (Molino et al. 2019b).

278 Focusing in *Struthiopteris*, several previous works are known to have described some aspects
279 of the spores of *S. spicant* (Tryon and Lugardon 1991; Passarelli et al. 2010; Passarelli 2007;
280 Moran et al. 2018; Lugardon 1965), which is the only taxon whose spores have been
281 described. The findings of these previous works agree in general with the observations made
282 here. The varieties within *Struthiopteris spicant* (*S. spicant* var. *homophyllum* and *S. spicant*
283 var. *pradae*) lacked any spore description until now. Only the size was reported in a recent
284 study of the complex *S. spicant* (Molino et al., 2019a). Our results show the absence of
285 relevant differences in spore traits between all these taxa, which indeed contribute to the idea
286 that the rank of variety is appropriate for the plants within this complex (Molino et al. 2019a).
287 We also report that the spore of *S. fallax* shows important differences in size and
288 ornamentation from the spores of *S. spicant*. This supports the idea that this plant, which was
289 considered as a variety of *S. spicant* until recently (Wasowicz et al. 2017), deserve a different
290 status at the species level (Molino et al. 2019a). *Struthiopteris castanea* spores were briefly
291 described by Mitui (1979), and his description agrees with what we have observed here in
292 more detail. The spores of this species are the biggest in *Struthiopteris*, resembling the spore
293 size of *Spicantopsis*, but again this could reflect the high ploidy level of this taxon.

294 Finally, it is remarkable the frequency in which we observed the perispore of the spores of all
295 the taxa coming off so easily, fact already mentioned in the study by Mitui (1979). Perhaps
296 this could be the reason why some other authors have erroneously reported that some
297 Blechnaceae do not have perispore (Ching 1940; Tagawa 1959).

298 In conclusion, from a taxonomic perspective, we show here that *Struthiopteris* and
299 *Spicantopsis* differ in sporangia and spores, particularly in the number and thickness of the
300 cells in the lips, sporangial size, and structure and ornamentation of perispore. These
301 characters are easy to study and could be very useful in the separation of both genera.
302 Furthermore, they add to some other meaningful morphological characters already discovered
303 by Molino et al. (2019b) –epidermal hairs, structure of indusia, etc.–, emphasizing the
304 monophyly of both genera, *Struthiopteris* and *Spicantopsis*. Other characters of the sporangia
305 and spores show differences that could be useful to identify species, subspecies, and varieties.
306 Finally, traits such as the perispore ornamentation, thickness and internal structure, are shared
307 between *Struthiopteris* and *Blechnidium* T. Moore (Moran et al., 2018), pointing at a closer
308 phylogenetic relationship of those than between *Struthiopteris* and *Spicantopsis*, fact that
309 coincides with what is stated in Molino *et al.* (2019b). The rest of characters studied here
310 remain unknown for *Blechnidium*, whose phylogenetic position sister to *Struthiopteris* /
311 *Spicantopsis* is striking and deserves further investigation.

312 To sum up the main characters that distinguish the taxa studied here, we propose the
313 following identification key regarding sporangium and spore traits. This key is especially
314 interesting for separating pairs of species in two cases, *Spicantopsis niponica* - *S. hancockii*
315 and *Struthiopteris castanea* - *S. spicant*, which are difficult to distinguish by
316 macromorphological characters.

317 The varieties of *S. spicant* could not be included in this key since we did not find any
318 differential traits regarding the sporangia or the spores.

319

320 Identification key

321

- 322 Sporangia lips formed by 4-7 cells which are <12.5 μm thick; spores with a compact
 323 perispore which is < 5 μm thick.....*Spicantopsis*
- 324 Sporangia lips formed by 2-3 cells which are >12.5 μm thick; spores with an alveolate
 325 perispore which is > 5 μm thick.*Struthiopteris*
- 326
- 327 *Spicantopsis*
- 328 1.- Spores with verrucate-granulate perispore.....*S. amabilis*
- 329 Spores with irregularly reticulate perispore.....2
- 330
- 331 2.- With posterior basal cells in the sporangia; 19-20 arcus cells; spores around 59x43
 332 μm*S. niponica*
- 333 Without posterior basal cells in the sporangia; 20-29 arcus cells; spores around 50x35
 334 μm*S. hancockii*
- 335
- 336 *Struthiopteris*
- 337 1.- Sporangium capsule > 300 μm ; spores >50 μm in length.....*S. castanea*
- 338 Sporangium capsule < 300 μm ; spores <50 μm in length.....2
- 339
- 340 2.- Spores around 44x32 μm ; perispore rugate, sharply angular; laesura almost as long as the
 341 spore.....*S. fallax*
- 342 Spores around 38-41x26-29 μm (this variation includes all the varieties); perispore slightly
 343 rugate; laesura not as long as the spore *S. spicant*
- 344

345 **IV. Acknowledgments**

346 The Universidad Complutense de Madrid partially supported this research through the
347 funding of a project PR26/16-20295, and a field trip to Iceland (International Mobility
348 Program 2016).

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VI. Table and Figures

423 **Table 1.** Comparison table of sporangia and spore characters for *Spicantopsis* and *Struthiopteris*.

Taxon	# arc cells	# cells lips	lip cells thickness (µm)	Capsule size (µm)	# cells epistomium	# cells hypostomium	pedicell length (µm)	Spore size (µm)	Perispore thickness (µm)	Perispore ornamentation	Perispore structure	Exospore
<i>Spicantopsis</i>												
<i>S. amabilis</i>	20–26	7	5-10	320-380	3-5	3-4	150-400	55.52 x 37.76	up to 5	verrucate–granulate	compact	smooth
<i>S. hancockii</i>	20–29	4-7	7.5-12.3	280-370	8	3	200-300	49.74 x 33.64	up to 5	irregular reticulate	compact	small bullae
<i>S. niponica</i>	19–20	5-6	7.4-12.3	280-370	8-10	3	180-200	59.29 x 42.48	up to 5	irregular reticulate	compact	small bullae
<i>Struthiopteris</i>												
<i>S. castanea</i>	16–20	2-3	27.5-37.5	340-460	5-8	4	150-250	56.26 x 41.87	up to 12	rugate	alveolate	smooth
<i>S. fallax</i>	13–21	3	12.5-17.5	210-250	3-8	3-5	120-300	43.33 x 31.83	up to 12	rugate	alveolate	smooth
<i>S. spicant</i> var. <i>spicant</i>	12–18	2-3	12.7-19	240-300	5-6	3-4	250-280	40.37 x 28.47	up to 12	rugate	alveolate	smooth
<i>S. spicant</i> var. <i>homophyllum</i>	12–19	2-3	12.5-17.5	230-280	4-7	3-6	170	38.01 x 26.63	up to 12	rugate	alveolate	smooth
<i>S. spicant</i> var. <i>pradae</i>	12–20	2-3	12.5-17.5	210-260	4-6	3-6	150-200	42.05 x 29.35	up to 12	rugate	alveolate	smooth

425

426 **Figure 1.** Photographs of herbarium specimens of representative plants of the genera

427 *Spicantopsis* and *Struthiopteris*: A) *Spicantopsis niponica* (Umemura 37, P 01406521). B)

428 *Struthiopteris spicant* (E. Blanco 1182, MA 564805). Scale bar = 3 cm in both.

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431 **Figure 2.** Schematic of a leptosporangiate vertical sporangium, typical of the Polypodiales,
 432 with indication of the main traits considered in this work. Terminology is based on Lellinger
 433 (1990) and Wilson (1959), except for the terms “rosette” and “lips”, from Prada et al. (2016),
 434 and “posterior cells of the annulus”, proposed here.

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437 **Figure 3.** Light microscope details of the sporangium stipe and stomial area in taxa of438 *Spicantopsis* (A & C) and *Struthiopteris* (B & D). A) complete sporangium of *S. niponica* (B.439 *Estébanez s.n.*, MACB 110657). B) *in situ* complete sporangium of *S. spicant* (*Gabriel y*440 *Galán s.n.* MACB 109622). C) details of the capsule of *S. niponica*, showing the stomial area

441 (*Estébanez s.n.*, MACB 110657). D) details of the capsule of *S. spicant*, showing the stomial
 442 area (*Gabriel y Galán s.n.*, MACB 109622). Ar = arcus; E-st = epistomium; H-st =
 443 hypostomium; In = indusium; L = lip; P = pedicel; Pbc = posterior basal cells; Ro = rosette.
 444 Bar = 80 μm in A, 90 μm in B, 65 μm in C, 50 μm in D.

445
 446 **Figure 4.** SEM details of the sporangium pedicel and stomium in taxa of *Spicantopsis* (A)
 447 and *Struthiopteris* (B-D). A) cross-section of the sporangium pedicel, showing the three-
 448 celled configuration at the rosette, *S. hancockii* (*Knapp 4311*, P 02435597). B–D: mature
 449 opened sporangia with complex stomium showing the lips, the epistomium and the
 450 hypostomium. B) *S. castanea* (*Mizushima 13853*, S 1982); C) *S. spicant* var. *spicant* (*Gabriel*
 451 *y Galán s.n.*, MACB 109622); D) *S. spicant* var. *homophyllum* (*Barrera s.n.*, MACB 32367).

452 Ar = arcus; E-st = epistomium; H-st = hypostomium; L = lip; P = pedicel. Scale bar = 60 μm

453 in A; 85 μm in B; 75 μm in C, D.

455 **Figure 5.** Details of the annulus in *Spicantopsis* (A-C) and *Struthiopteris*, (D-H) showing the
456 thickened cells of the arcus. A) *S. amabilis* (*Faurié 5612*, P 01406648), 20 cells. B) *S.*
457 *hancockii* (*Knapp 4311*, P 02435597), 20 cells. C) *S. niponica* (*Tagawa & Iwatsuki 3014*, P
458 01575937), 19 cells. D) *S. castanea* (*Mizushima 13853*, S 1982), 19 cells. E) *S. fallax*, 18
459 cells (*Gabriel y Galán & Wasowicz s.n.*, MACB 109359). F) *S. spicant* var. *spicant* (*Gabriel y*
460 *Galán s.n.*, MACB 109622), 16 cells. G) *S. spicant* var. *homophyllum* (*Barrera s.n.*, MACB
461 32367), 13 cells. H) *S. spicant* var. *pradae* (*Molino et al. s.n.*, MACB 110654), 12 cells. Bar
462 = 75 μm in B, E and F; 80 μm in C; 85 μm in D; 90 μm in A, G and H.

464 **Figure 6.** Spores of *Spicantopsis*: A: *S. amabilis* (Faurié 5612, P 01406648). B: *S. hancockii*
465 (*Knapp 4311*, P 02435597). C: *S. niponica* var. *niponica* (Tagawa & Iwatsuki 3014,P
466 01575937). Spores of *Struthiopteris*: D: *S. castanea* (Saito s.n., TNS 792168). E: *S. fallax*
467 (*Gabriel y Galán & Wasowicz s.n.*, MACB 109359). F: *S. spicant* var. *spicant* (*Gabriel y*
468 *Galán s.n.*, MACB 110658). G: *S. spicant* var. *homophyllum* (*Barrera s.n.*, MACB 32367).
469 H: *S. spicant* var. *pradae* (*Molino et al. s.n.*, MACB 110654). Bar =15 µm in all, except A, E
470 and G =10 µm.
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474 **Figure 7.** Fragmented perispore of spores from *Spicantopsis* species (left) with details (right):
 475 A, B. *S. amabilis* (Faurié 5612, P 01406648). C, D: *S. hancockii* (Knapp 4311, P 02435597).
 476 Fragmented perispore of spores from *Struthiopteris* species (left) with details (right): E, F: *S.*
 477 *castanea* (Saito s.n., TNS 792168). G, H: *S. spicant* (Gabriel y Galán s.n., MACB 110658).
 478 Bar = 20 µm for the complete spores (left) and 10 µm for the details (right).

479

480 VII. Appendix 1

481 List of material used, with basic voucher information, ordered by taxon:

482 *Spicantopsis amabilis* (Makino) Nakai. JAPAN: Faurié 5612 07/1904, (P01406648);
 483 Honshū: Echigo, Tsugawa, Togashi 1576 16/09/1957, (P01406637); Mie, Utobi, Seto 6672
 484 23/11/1956, (P01608624); Nara, Shōfuken-dake, Tawaga & Iwatsuki 5129 4/08/1962,
 485 (P01575933); Tochigi, Tagawa & Iwatsuki 1913 13/09/1958, (P01608623). *Spicantopsis*
 486 *hancockii* (Hance) Masam. TAIWAN: Chiayi: Alishan, Arisan, Iwasaki s.n. 22/07/1970,
 487 (TNS832514); Taipei: Beitou, Knapp 3338 18/01/2014, (P02439073); Taitung: Taiwu,
 488 Knapp 3430 2/06/2014, (P02439164); Yilan: Nan'ao Township, Taipingshan, Knapp 4311
 489 3/09/2016, (P02435597); *ibidimen*, Knapp & Huang 239 5/12/2005, (P02436496).
 490 *Spicantopsis niponica* (Kunze) Nakai. JAPAN: *without collector, locality and date*,
 491 (TNS01147387); Honshū: Hyōgo, Myōkō-san, Hikami-gun, Tagawa & Iwatsuki 3014
 492 23/09/1960, (P01575937); Kanawaga, Kantō, Yokohama, Maximowicz s.n. 1862,
 493 (P01406592); Wakayama, Tanabe-shi, Nakahechi-cho, Mizukami, B. Estébanez s.n.,
 494 21/08/2017 (MACB110657). *Struthiopteris castanea* (Makino & Nemoto) Nakai. JAPAN:
 495 Honshū: Fukui, Imadate-gun, Ikeda-cho, Kanmuri-yama, Saito s.n. no date (TNS792168);
 496 Hyogo, Mikana-gun, Onsen-cho, Ueyama-kkogen, Tobayashi s.n. 25/07/1999, (TNS700642);
 497 Shinano, Shumominochi-gun, Minochi-mura, Mizushima 13853 28/06/1956, (S1982).

498 ***Struthiopteris fallax*** (Lange) S. Molino, Gabriel y Galán & Wasowicz. ICELAND:
499 Deildartunguhver, *Wasowicz & Gabriel y Galán s.n.*, jul 2016, (MACB109359) (3
500 individuals). ***Struthiopteris spicant*** (L.) Weiss var. ***spicant***. SPAIN: Canary Islands: Anaga,
501 Tenerife, *Gabriel y Galán s.n.* 14/09/2017, (MACB110658); Cantabria: Camaleño, Cosgaya,
502 *Gabriel y Galán s.n.* 8/10/2016, (MACB109622); Galicia: Monte Aloya, Tuy, *Pajarón &*
503 *Pangua s.n.* 15/07/1993, (MACB59142). ***Struthiopteris spicant*** var. ***homophyllum*** (Merino)
504 Gabriel y Galán & R. Pino. PORTUGAL: Braga, Vieira do Minho, *Prada s.n.* 1/10/2004,
505 (MACB109621). SPAIN: Galicia: between Tabagón y Tomiño, *Gabriel y Galán s.n.*
506 19/03/2016, (MACB109617); Santiago, Cantaleta, *Barrera s.n.* 29/07/1967, (MACB32367);
507 Santiago, *no collector* 29/07/2007, (MA824045). Salamanca: Batuecas, *Gabriel y Galán s.n.*
508 15/05/2016, (MACB109626). ***Struthiopteris spicant*** var. ***pradae*** S. Molino & Gabriel y
509 Galán. SPAIN: Asturias: Valdés, Paladeporre, *Gabriel y Galán s.n.* 22/03/2016,
510 (MACB109613); *ibidem*, 3/08/2016, (MACB109615); Burgos: Sierra de San Millán, *Fuentes*
511 *s.n.* 27/09/1975. (MACB5994), Zamora: Aciberos, *Molino, Seral, Gabriel y Galán & de la*
512 *Fuente s.n.* 23/09/2017, (MACB110654).

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